

The influence of perceived family supports and barriers on personal variables in a Spanish sample of secondary school science-technology students

Running Head: Family Supports, STEM on Students' Self-Efficacy

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Acknowledgements: We gratefully acknowledge the assistance of R.W. Lent for sending the scales used in this study.

Funding: This article is based on work supported by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (Spain) (EDU-2010-17233).

Disclosure statement: No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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There is a need to improve students' motivation in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). Student's academic choices are significantly influenced by parental behaviors, and even more so by how those behaviors are perceived by the students.

Perceived supports and barriers are those situations that a student encounters in their path, determining their future career decisions. The purpose of this study is to determine the influence of perceived family support/barriers on cognitive-personal variables: self-efficacy beliefs, interest, outcome expectations and goals in a Spanish sample of 10th-grade science-technology students ($N = 2,359$), along with the influence of gender and emotional state effect, through Social Cognitive Career Theory. A path analysis was performed to test the framework model. Findings show that perceived family supports can influence self-efficacy, interests, outcome expectations and goals. Multiple-group analysis showed that weight values did not differ by gender. We concluded that a negative emotional state when faced with science-technology tasks also gives rise to low self-efficacy beliefs about solving these kinds of problems, and therefore a lack of interest in technology and poor outcome expectations and goals. When students perceive parental support around their STEM lessons, their emotional state also improves in these subjects. Overall, these results emphasize the importance of considering parental involvement in career guidance for adolescents.

Keywords: STEM; family support/barriers; self-efficacy beliefs; secondary students; gender; emotional state; social cognitive career theory; multiple-group SEM.

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One of the priorities of European Union education policies is to improve students' motivation in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) (European Commission, 2012). An increase in the number of students and graduates in scientific and technical courses is desired in order to raise the European profile in scientific research and economic development (Rodríguez-Menéndez, Inda-Caro, & Fernández-García, 2016). It seems imperative therefore to identify “factors that may enhance or impede young adolescents' career development” (Keller & Whiston, 2008, p. 199). Martincin and Stead (2015) reported the need to have a broader understanding of the factors that influence students' vocational choices. This may enable more appropriate interventions and may help families to create more interest in STEM areas. This seems crucial given the demonstrated lack of scientific vocation and low attainment levels exhibited by many students in science-technology subjects (Vázquez & Manassero, 2009). In this study, we analyze three elements (perceived parent support and barriers, gender and emotional state) which are important in reaching the European Union objective. Spain is undergoing significant changes in the job market. Recent studies have identified the need to invest more, and more effectively, in human capital so that future workers acquire the STEM knowledge and skills to respond to the future demands of technological progress. It seems that the Spanish labor market is going to lack people with these abilities and consequently it is necessary to develop educational networks to promote STEM knowledge in the Spanish context (Doménech, García, Montáñez, & Neut, 2018).

Families, particularly parents, play a central role in shaping their children's professional aspirations and in encouraging them to explore their educational and professional possibilities (e.g., Fouad, Kim, Ghosh, Chang, & Figueiredo, 2016; Hargrove, Creagh, & Burgess, 2002; Sawitri, Creed, & Zimmer-Gembeck, 2014; Turner, Steward, & Lapan, 2004; Whiston &

Keller, 2004). Using social cognitive career theory (SCCT) as a conceptual model, which we explain below, we examined how *perceived family support and barriers* affect different factors identified by vocational educational researchers as elements that can promote or impede STEM career paths: self-efficacy beliefs, interest, outcome expectations and goals. In this sense, Byars-Winston, Diestelmann, Savoy and Hoyt (2017), highlighted 'self-efficacy shapes motivation and commitment in the form of aspirations, academic behavior, and career pursuits' (p. 645). The study was carried out with a sample of students in lower secondary education in the of science and technology branch in Spain (students in Spain choose to pursue one of three branches in secondary education which focus to a greater or lesser extent on science and technology or the arts and humanities.) between 15-18 years old. Adolescents perceive parental supports/barriers and this perception may influence how they see their own academic and professional competences (Gushue & Whitson, 2006), thereby affecting their future studies and work. The quality of the parent-child relationship has been associated with the development of self-efficacy beliefs (Manzano-Sánchez, Outley, González, & Matarrita-Cascante, 2018). For example, parents who provide emotional support to their children while they are struggling to complete a difficult task can help to facilitate children's self-efficacy beliefs. It is therefore fundamental to consider parental supports/barriers in order to not only understand students' career decisions, but also to intervene effectively so that they can reach their academic goals.

In addition, we place special emphasis on the influence of *gender*. We support a concept of gender which emphasizes human beings' plurality, exceeding the limitations of a restrictive dual concept of gender; gender is not only based on sexual differences but in fact on a wider concept within a heterogenic social context (Benhabib, 2006). Although gender differences have diminished in the last 20 years (Whitmarsh & Keyser Wentworth, 2012), they are still active when deciding what courses to study (Gati & Perez, 2014). Research has found some

evidence for gender differences in academic intentions and career goals (Chachashvili-Bolotin, Milner-Bolotin, & Lissitsa, 2016; Evers & Sieverding, 2015). Moreover, women score lower than men in self-efficacy beliefs and thus have been discouraged from choosing traditionally male-dominated areas such as technology (Navarro et al., 2019; Byars-Winston et al. 2017). Previous research has shown that men are more likely than women to seek occupations in STEM related fields (Gati & Perez, 2014). This pattern of preferences apparently constrains the set of occupations and jobs perceived as suitable career options for many women. There is still a gender gap in this area and many women are missing out on a future with great potential for involvement in innovation and technological progress (OECD, 2017). In addition, the STEM field is not being benefited from the diversity and perspectives which can be provided by these absent women. It is important to investigate the reasons for the low presence of women in these vocational fields, and perceived family support/barriers may be one of them (Rodríguez-Menéndez et al., 2016).

Finally, we also considered the personal variable *emotional state*. A positive mood can boost one's beliefs in self-efficacy, while anxiety can undermine it. A certain level of emotional stimulation can create an energizing feeling that can contribute to strong performances (Margolis & McCabe, 2006). Emotional states such as anxiety and stress, along with one's mood, provide information about self-efficacy beliefs (DuBow & Kaminsky, 2019, Cheryan, Ziegler, Montoya & Jiang, 2017). Typically, optimism and a positive mood enhance self-efficacy, whereas depression, despair, or a sense of despondency diminish it. Besides, as with the other sources, 'it is not the intensity of the physical indicator or mood state itself that is important, but the individual's interpretation of it' (Pajares, 2006, p. 351). So, negative 'emotional states may contribute to lower self-efficacy outcome expectations, and interest' (Rodríguez-Menéndez et al., 2016, p. 310).

The SCCT model as a possible explanation of students' academic choices, career preferences and academic performance

To achieve the goals of our study, we used social cognitive career theory (SCCT) as the theoretical reference framework (Lent & Brown, 2019). This theory was developed by Lent and colleagues (1994), and holds that the configuration of vocational careers is influenced both by cognitive-personal variables and contextual and personal factors (Lent, Brown & Hackett, 1994, 2000; Sheu & Bordon, 2017). Cognitive-personal variables include four dimensions: self-efficacy beliefs (people's beliefs about the ability to successfully perform tasks in a specific domain), outcome expectations (personal estimation of the results expected when an academic choice is made), interest (preferences for certain activities) and goals (disposition to persist with an academic option or to achieve a particular result). Although those variables referred to student background or perceived support and barriers have not been included in the core variables of the SCCT theory, they need to be studied as long as they do influence the already mentioned core variables, showing a predictive value. Contextual factors are those variables that a person perceives to have a potential effect which helps (supports), or hinders (barriers), their efforts to achieve certain academic or professional goals. Examples of supports include the feeling that family members/peers support personal decisions; while a barrier could be receiving negative comments about a chosen course from friends. This model argues that an understanding of the barriers which interfere with or support career development is essential for determining whether the person has considered all possible options and the effectiveness of their decision-making skills (Lent et al., 2000). This theory has been verified over recent decades, demonstrating high predictive value in identifying career development (Fouad & Santana, 2017; Lent, Brown, Nota, & Soresi, 2003; Lent & Brown, 2019; Lent, Paixao, Da Silva, & Leitao, 2010; Navarro, Flores, & Worthington, 2007; Nugent et al., 2015; Turner et al., 2004).

SCCT and contextual variables

People's perceptions of social supports and barriers have a continuing influence on their careers as well as on their self-efficacy beliefs (Lent, 2005). When people perceive greater social supports and fewer career barriers, they have stronger beliefs in their ability to do well in their chosen vocational domain (Lent et al., 2001; Lent et al., 2003). Recent researches indicate that perceived supports/barriers are important in occupational decisions (Ali, Brown, & Loh, 2017; Mozahem, Ghanem, Hamieh, & Shoujaa 2019; Navarro et al., 2019). Fouad et al. (2010) called for increased research to study the interactions with different environmental variables, and specifically family supports and barriers. Variables such as family support, parental aspirations and expectations play a more important role in career development than parental occupations, socioeconomic status or class (Metheny & McWhirter, 2013; Whiston & Keller, 2004).

The influence of perceived family supports and barriers on STEM students

Previous research has concluded that perceived parental support has a greater influence on students' career expectations than the support of teachers, peers or school counselors (Fouad, Chang, Wang & Singh, 2017). Moreover, this support also helps to overcome the impact of perceived barriers (Lent et al., 2010). Various studies of secondary school students have confirmed that perceived parental support influences self-efficacy beliefs (Ali, McWhirter, & Chronister, 2005; Flores, Navarro, Smith & Ploszaj, 2006; Garriot, Hudyma, Keene & Santiago, 2015; Gushue & Whitson, 2006; Keller & Whiston, 2008; Navarro et al., 2007; Nugent et al., 2015; Turner et al., 2004; Turner & Lapan, 2002), goals (Flores & O'Brien, 2002) and outcome expectations (Turner et al., 2004). Nevertheless, 'family factors cannot be examined in isolation' (Fouad & Kantamneni, 2008, p. 420). Only some recent studies such as Fouad & Santana (2017) or Garriot et al. (2014) have used SCCT to analyze the direct

influence of parental support on learning experiences which affect the model's core variables. In others studies, parental involvement directly predicted math/science self-efficacy beliefs and outcome expectations and indirectly predicted math/science interests and goals (Byars-Winston & Fouad (2008); Sallee et al., 2019). Similarly, parental opinions have been shown to influence children's performance and self-efficacy beliefs (Ashby & Schoon, 2010; Bandura, Barbaranelli, Caprara, & Pastorelli, 2001).

The influence of gender and emotional state on SCCT cognitive-personal variables

SCCT has the strength to incorporate explicit personal variables into career development and choice models. Our study examined the influence of two personal variables on cognitive-personal variables of the SCCT model: gender and emotional state. These two variables are at the same level as contextual variables, supports and barriers, in an external orbit to the core variables of self-efficacy, outcome expectations, goals and interest. In addition, it should be considered that recent studies have shown that affective states have a stronger influence in women than in men when self-efficacy beliefs are the focus (Byars-Winston & Rogers, 2019).

As long as the traditional socialization process that boys and girls experience in technology and science must be considered, the study of gender differences in these variables seems determinant. Although the original SCCT model suggested that socio-cognitive variables did not seem to be moderated by students' gender, SCCT variables can help to explain interest and major-choice goals in both women and men. Lent et al.'s (2018, p. 28) recent meta-analytical path analysis of the socio-cognitive choice model looking at gender states 'the model of choice fits well with the data in analyses separated by gender (...), which suggests that the predictive utility of the model can be generalized through these grouping variables (that is, it can help explain the STEM interests and options of women and men)'. This research found that 'several sets of coefficients did differ, both statistically and practically, as

a function of gender and race/ethnicity within the multigroup analyses' (Lent et al., 2018, p. 28). Barriers were seen as a mechanism to explain women's restricted professional aspirations and the divergence between their skills and their achievements (Mozahem et al., 2019).

Perceived parental supports or barriers are also influenced by gender. Some studies have indicated that parents believe boys are better than girls in mathematics (Tiedemann, 2000) or that boys' educational performances could benefit from raised parental aspirations (Ashby & Schoon, 2010). Nevertheless, whereas Navarro et al. (2007) showed that women perceived more social support and fewer social barriers, studies by Casas & Blanco (2017) and Kenny and Bledsoe (2005), found no gender differences in perceived family support, although boys perceived more barriers than girls. In general, research has shown gender differences in self-efficacy beliefs regarding technology and interest in technology, partly due to the gender role during the socialization process and partly due to the way in which social supports and barriers affect how men and women organize and understand their own careers (Kantamneni & Fouad, 2013). For example, in Luzzo and McWhirter's (2001) study, women expected to face more barriers (Fort & Murariu, 2018), negative comments and gender discrimination than men. The qualitative research by Zeldin and Pajares (2000), and Zeldin, Britner and Pajares (2008), indicated that perceived support could help girls to be more resilient, to overcome academic and social hurdles and to counteract negative messages produced by their social context (Mozahem et al., 2019). However, those researchers did not study the influence of parental perception regarding gender stereotypes when choosing technology courses such as whether technology courses were for boys and not for girls. It is necessary to examine students' perceptions of their parents' beliefs about how their choices are going to determine their academic futures, the options they have to achieve a more satisfying personal life, whether their decisions have parental agreement, families' encouragement to get good marks

in technology subjects or whether families reinforce students' decisions to study technology subjects.

We included personal variable *emotional state* due to the little existing research assessing its influence on cognitive-person variables in the SCCT model. Britner and Pajares (2001, 2006), basing their work on Bandura's theoretical model, indicated that one of the four factors influencing the development of self-efficacy beliefs is the emotional state in which the person thinks about or does a task. Both studies showed that in the presence of anxiety, self-efficacy beliefs are likely to be low, while the opposite is seen when the individual is relaxed. Moreover, low self-efficacy beliefs about technology courses can be related to stress and anxiety (Williams & Subich, 2006; DuBow & Kaminsky, 2019) or even lack of interest in technological areas. People expect to have negative outcomes when they study any technology topic. In short, the emotional state is defined as feelings of anxiety about coping with technology-related tasks. It also assesses whether the person feels nervous or uncomfortable when they think about technology, or whether a student does not give up until a technology-related assignment has been completed. Difficulties in maintaining levels of performance in those kinds of situations may well affect peoples' perceptions of self-efficacy.

Study objectives

The purpose of the study is to examine how perceived family support and barriers affect the SCCT cognitive-personal variables of self-efficacy beliefs, interest, outcome expectations and goals, in a sample of secondary school students in the science and technology branches. In this context, we have arrived at the following research questions:

1. What is the extent of the influence of perceived family supports and barriers on the core variables of the SCCT model in science and technology students?

2. How do students' stress levels about different activities involving technology (classes, examinations, etc.) determine how they cope with the challenges of technology courses?
3. Are there gender-based differences in the influence of perceived family supports/barriers and stress levels on the core variables of the SCCT model?

To respond to these three questions, we propose the following hypotheses:

1. Perceived family supports and barriers have a direct effect on the core variables of the SCCT model given their predictive value regarding self-efficacy beliefs, outcome expectations, goals, and interests by gender.
2. Perceived family barriers and supports correlate negatively and significantly with each other, so that the greater the perception of family support, the lower the perception of barriers, and vice-versa (Lent et al., 2000).
4. The stress levels experienced in different activities involving technology (classes, examinations, etc.) negatively influence how students perceive their own competences for successfully coping with the challenges of technical courses, their level of interest in this field of learning, and their outcome expectations and goals.
5. The influence of perceived family supports/barriers and stress levels on self-efficacy beliefs, interest and outcome expectations is different in boys and girls.

Method

Participants

We selected probability proportional to size (PPS) as our sampling technique (Foreman, 1991; Joshi, 2018). This procedure is very useful when the sampling units are very different in size, as long as all districts have the same probability of being included in the sample, regardless of

their size. In addition, researchers can plan their work more effectively because a specific number of respondents are selected in each unit to be interviewed. The schools assessed in this study represent all of the districts in the Principality of Asturias. We used the geographic distribution from the Asturian Society for Economic and Industrial Research (SADEI, 2019) for the division of the region into eight industrial and economic zones: Oriente, Nalón, Caudal, Gijón, Oviedo, Narcea, Avilés and Eo-Navia. The following process was used to arrive at the final sample. Firstly, assuming an error of .01, the final sample size was set at 2,400. The population of lower secondary students in the entire region was 7,109. A weight was assigned to each of the eight areas. This was calculated by dividing the n of each district by the total N of the population. The “*district n*” to create the sample was the product of the weight reflected by the “estimated n ” ($n = 2,400$).

Schools in each zone were selected as follows. First, we determined how many schools were needed in each district to achieve the “*district n*”. The “*district n*” needed to create the sample was divided by the average number of students per school in that district (school number, SN). Secondly, the schools were ranked from largest to smallest number of students; then, cumulative frequencies and the cumulative number of students (SCN) for each school were calculated. The district sample interval ($SI = SCN/SN$) was also estimated; the SI value was used to select a random number from a table (RN). The selection of schools was implemented using the following algorithm: school 1 = $SI * RN$; school 2 = $SI * (RN + 1)$; and so on to complete the number of chosen schools (SN). Subsequently, schools were selected with SCN values equivalent to school 1, school 2, etc. These steps were repeated for each of the eight districts.

In Spain, when the students are finishing the 9th grade (the end of Compulsory Education), they have to choose between three different Upper Secondary Education tracks for the 10th grade: Arts; Social Sciences and Humanities; and Technology.

For this study, the final sample was made up of 2,359 10th grade students who had freely decided to take science-technology subjects within the technology branch. About half (1,197) were girls and 1,162 were boys. Students were aged between 15 and 18 years old, ($M = 15.6$, $SD = 1.2$). The age distribution was not normal, with measures of skewness and kurtosis greater than 1 in absolute terms; 87% had a mean age of 16 years. The analysis of age by gender gave statistically significant differences ($U = 703.25$, $p < .001$). In girls, the mean age was 15.6 ($SD = 1.33$) and in boys it was 16 ($SD = 1.1$).

Procedure

Forty-six schools from the Principality of Asturias (Spain) participated in the study. Data was collected by the research team. During the process, the researchers explained the main objectives and then asked the students to complete the questionnaire. Participation in the study was voluntary, and students were free to leave the room if they did not want to participate. There was no remuneration for participation and all parents gave their consent.

Instruments

The instrument was created using various scales. The reason that justifies their use is due to the fact that Pajares and Fouad were the pioneers (also with Lent) in this research line. We got the authorization to adapt Pajares's and Lent's instruments into Spanish. Although we are conscious that this instrument is not a recent one, the translation into Spanish has allowed the research team to adapt it to the actual society and to the Spanish culture.

a) *Technology Grade Self-Efficacy Scale*. This scale is a Spanish translation and adaptation of the Science Grade Self-Efficacy Scale (Britner & Pajares, 2001, 2006). The scale contains 3 items assessing high school students' self-confidence in their abilities to successfully perform technology-related tasks. Participants rated each item (e.g., "How confident are you that you will get an "A+" in technology subjects?") on a 6-point scale ranging from 1 (not confident at

all) to 6 (completely confident). High scores indicate high levels of technology self-efficacy.

In the Spanish sample the scale yielded a Cronbach's α of .88.

b) *Technology Sources of Self-Efficacy Scale* is the Spanish translation of the Sources of Self-Efficacy Science Scale developed by Britner & Pajares (2006). The Scale has fifty-nine items which measure social persuasion, vicarious experiences and physiological states. The answers range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree). The internal consistency reliability of the original version was $\alpha = .90$ for mastery experiences, .88 for social persuasion, .80 for vicarious experiences, and .91 for emotional state. In our study, three factors were obtained from factor analyses: social persuasion, vicarious experiences and physiological states. The factor called 'social supports' refers to social persuasion, describing support students get from significant others, for example: 'My friends often come to me for help in technology'. In our sample this factor showed a coefficient of .96. The second factor is called 'social barriers' and considers vicarious experiences, i.e. variables which may include barriers for the student's choice of degree, such as: 'I am not as good at science as most of the kids in my class'. Internal consistency in our sample was .84. 'Emotional state' measures the anxiety students feel about technology/computer classes, for example: 'Technology tests are usually easy for me'. The full sample had an alpha coefficient of .83 (Inda-Caro, Rodríguez-Menéndez, & Peña-Calvo, 2016).

c) The *Technology Outcome Expectations Scale* is an adaptation of the Mathematics/Science Outcome Expectations Scale (MSOES) developed by Fouad, Smith, & Enochs (1997). This scale, which consists of 9 items, assesses high school students' beliefs about the potential consequences of studying Technology subjects in high school (e.g., 'Studying Technology subjects in high school will improve my job prospects'). The answers range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree). The alpha coefficient in the study by Fouad and Smith (1996)

was .71, and .70 in the case of Fouad et al. (1997). The result in the Spanish sample was .95 (Inda-Caro et al., 2016).

d) The *Technology Intentions and Goals Scale* was adapted from the Math/Science Intentions and Goals Scale (MSIGS, Fouad et al., 1997). This instrument consists of 4 items which assess high school students' intentions to keep studying technology-related courses at college. Answers range from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 6 (*strongly agree*) (e.g., 'I plan to do a technology-related degree at university'). Fouad and Smith's (1996) study had an alpha of .66, while Fouad et al. (1997) gave an internal consistency of .74. It is important to note that in the Spanish sample 'outcome expectations' included three items which measured goals, with loadings under .35. When a two-factor solution (outcome expectations and goals) was considered, the fit was poor (Inda-Caro et al., 2016).

e) The *Technology Interest Scale* was an adaptation of the Engineering Fields Questionnaire created by Lent, Brown, Nota, et al. (2003) (Inda-Caro et al., 2016). The main objective of this scale was to assess an individual's interest in technology-related activities via 9 items. An example is: 'I enjoy learning about technology'. Answers ranged from 1 (very low interest) to 6 (very high interest). The reliability of the original version was .83 and .80 (Lent, Brown, Nota, et al, 2003). In the Spanish sample the study gave an internal consistency of .94 (Inda-Caro et al., 2016).

e) *Perceived family supports and barriers* (Inda-Caro et al., 2016): these two factors were obtained by collecting the instrument items which assessed family issues: six items from the *Technology Sources of Self-Efficacy Scale*, five items from the *Technology Intentions and Goals Scale*, and, finally, 2 items from *Gender-role Attitudes* (Table 1).

Table 1

Factorial structure obtained

Items selected	Mean	SD	DI	Family Sources
My father believes that I have high technology/computer ability	3.97	1.81	.66	Support
My mother believes that I have high technology/computer ability	4.09	1.74	.65	Support
No one of my family is any good at technology/computer	2.70	1.74	-.09	Barrier
My family believes that I can do well in technology/computer subjects	4.29	1.73	.63	Support
My father encourages me to get good grades in technology/computer	4.55	1.78	.47	Support
My mother encourages me to get good grades in technology/computer	4.70	1.68	.48	Support
Selecting subjects to do the next year will likely allow me to have a career that is valued by my family	4.63	1.68	.52	Support
I will study for the career my parents want for me	2.12	1.59	.22	Support
My father believes if I get good grades in technology/computer then I will have a better future career	4.55	2.08	.55	Support
My mother believes if I get good grades in technology/computer then I will have a better future career	4.60	1.82	.57	Support
My family has been very valuable in choosing the subjects of my next course	4.22	2.15	.36	Support
My mother believes that technology/computer is for boys	2.22	1.79	.06	Barrier
My father believes that technology/computer is for boys	2.22	1.79	.06	Barrier

Note. *SD* = Standard Deviation; *DI* = Discrimination Index

Results

We performed structural equation modeling with the M-Plus program (Muthen & Muthen, 2010). Our aim was to show the influence of family supports and barriers on the main factors of the SCCT model, considering the gender variable. Prior to the path analysis, we examined Pearson correlations between factors in both girls and boys, as shown in Table 2. We found a considerable correlation between perceived family supports and self-efficacy beliefs, outcome expectations/goals and interests. Correlations between perceived family barriers and these variables were not high. For boys there was no correlation between perceived family supports and barriers. In girls, there was a correlation between these factors, $-.06$ ($p < .05$). The following indexes of fit were evaluated: CFI (Comparative fit index), TLI (Tucker-Lewis index), RMSEA (Root mean square error of approximation) and SRMR (Standardized root mean square residual).

Table 1

Summary of Intercorrelations, Means, and Standard Deviations for Scores on dimensions of the model as a Function of Gender

Dimensions of Model	1	2	3	4	5	6	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1. Self-Efficacy	-	.25***	.46***	.39***	-.08	-.26 ***	3.76	1.61
2. Outcome expectations/Goals	.24***	-	.17***	.50***	-.03	-.33***	3.92	1.24
3. Interests	.45***	.20***	-	.62***	.08 ***	-.37***	2.16	1.39
4. Perceived family supports	.45***	.48***	.59***	-	.00	-.39***	4.19	1.06

5. Perceived family barriers	-0.03	-.07*	.03	-.06*	-	.11***	2.40	0.30
6. Emotional State	-.27***	-.30***	-.41***	-.37***	.08*	-	0.21	1.24
<i>M</i>	3.78	3.93	2.17	4.15	2.35	0.15		
<i>SD</i>	1.57	1.26	1.38	1.07	1.26	1.22		

Note. Intercorrelations for boys ($n = 1,162$) are presented above the diagonal, and intercorrelations for girls ($n = 1,197$) are presented below the diagonal. Means and standard deviations for boys students are presented in the vertical columns, and means and standard deviations for girls are presented in the horizontal rows.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

We carried out a multiple-group analysis to explore the influences of perceived family support and barriers on the core of SCCT. Four models were considered. Firstly, a separate model for girls and boys (Model 1 and Model 2), then a model with unconstrained loads (Model 3), and subsequently a structural weights constrained model (Model 4), with the same weights set for girls and boys. Table 3 depicts the indexes of fit for the alternative models, following experts' recommendations to report several indices of model fit (Hoyle, 1995). The data demonstrated better fit in the constrained model; the χ^2 test indicated that there were differences ($\Delta\chi^2 = 19.01, p < .01$), therefore we concluded that weightings were the same for girls and boys.

Table 3.

Fit Indices for Models tested

Model	χ^2	df	p	CFI	TLI	RMSEA	SRMR	χ^2 diff
Model 1. Girls	8.98	2	.01	.99	.97	.05	.03	
Model 2. Boys	16.82	2	.00	.99	.94	.08	.03	
Model 3. Unconstrained	25.80	4	.00	.99	.96	.07	.03	
Model 4. Constrained weights	6.79	6	.34	1.00	.99	.01	.01	Model 3-4 = 19.01**

Note. Girls = 1,197. Boys = 1,162. CFI = Comparative Fit index; TLI= Tucker-Lewis index; RMSEA = Root mean square error of approximation; SRMR = Standardized root mean square residual

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

As shown in Figure 1, perceived family supports were strongly predictive of self-efficacy beliefs, interests, outcome expectations and goals. The paths for perceived family barriers to SCCT central factors were not significant, with the exception of the path from family barriers to self-efficacy in the boys' group ($\beta = -.07, p < .01$) and the path from perceived family barriers to interest. The influence was positive for both girls and boys. In boys ($\beta = .11, p < .05$) the influence was greater than in girls ($\beta = .08, p < .05$). This could be the result of

several gender stereotypes towards technology and computer studies. Another reason for this result could be located in the definition of the interest factor, which gathered negative attitudes or actions towards technology, for instance, lack of interest or feeling bored when facing technology or computers. Nevertheless, we have to note the low correlation between these factors for girls ($r = .03$) and boys ($r = .08$). In fact, this correlation was run in the unconstrained model, finding no fit for either girls or boys. The emotional state was more important in this model, in which social supports and barriers were only family factors. The paths from this factor to self-efficacy, interests and outcome expectations were significant and the path coefficients were larger than the model in which all social supports and barriers appeared (family, teacher, peer and financial) (Rodríguez-Menéndez et al., 2016). This factor assessed anxiety levels when students had to deal with technology-related matters: the ability and strength to solve difficult technology-related questions, or merely feeling nervous due to technology. Figure 1 shows that the influence of emotional state on interest was greater for girls than for boys. The significant weights of the paths were equal for boys and girls. Lent et al. (2013) indicated that social supports and barriers had an inverse relationship; we found the same in our study, with both family supports and barriers having a negative relationship.

Figure 1. Path model depicting influence of perceived family supports and barriers (N = 2,359).

Note. Multiple-group path analysis by gender. Estimation procedure was maximum likelihood. Paths coefficients are the standardized weights. For Girls, R^2 self-efficacy = 22%; R^2 Outcome expectations = 25% and R^2 interests = 43%. For Boys, R^2 self-efficacy = 17%; R^2 Outcome expectations = 27% and R^2 interests = 46%. G = girls; B = boys.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Discussion

The results of the study show that the students' perceptions about their family attitudes and beliefs about technology courses can influence how adolescents shape their career development. While the influence of perceived family supports on all the core SCCT variables (self-efficacy beliefs, outcome expectations, goals and interest) was shown in girls and boys, perception of family barriers was found to have less influence.

We concluded that the greater the perceived family support, the stronger the adolescents' beliefs about their own ability to succeed in technology-related fields, the greater their interest in technology, the better their outcome expectations, and the greater their desire to persevere in their studies and professional performance. These results are in line with earlier research (Ali et al., 2005; Cheryan et al, 2017; Flores et al., 2006; Flores & O'Brien, 2002; Fouad &

Santana, 2017; Garriot et al. 2015, Gushue & Whitson, 2006; Hargrove et al., 2002; Keller & Whiston 2008; Navarro et al., 2007; Nugent et al., 2015; Turner et al., 2004).

While the perception of family supports predicts self-efficacy in both gender groups, perceived family barriers did the same in boys, but not in girls. This is the only gender difference found in the path analysis to verify the model. This confirms the original SCCT model, which predicted that its utility was not modified by student gender, the variables of the model being able to explain career development regardless of gender. The influence between self-efficacy beliefs, interests, outcome expectations and goals was not conditioned by gender in our study. In spite of the fact that perceived family barriers did not predict outcome expectations or goals in male or in female secondary education students, our findings show that they had a minor influence on interest in technology in both gender groups. One reason for this may be that the interest domain collected negative items, which could bias the relationship between the two factors.

Likewise, perceived family barriers predicted self-efficacy beliefs, but only in boys and with low statistical significance, with path analysis showing a negative relationship between the two domains.

Perception of family barriers was more decisive in boys in terms of their self-efficacy beliefs than in girls; the influence of perceived family supports on self-efficacy beliefs was greater for girls than for boys. Lent et al. (2018) also concluded that 'the negative relation of barriers to self-efficacy was stronger in the male than in the female samples'.

These results confirm the conclusions of various studies indicating that despite girls expecting to find more social and family barriers (Luzzo & McWhirter, 2001), the support they received had a greater influence than in boys, helping them to overcome academic and social hurdles and counteracting negative messages picked up in their social environment

(Zeldin & Pajares, 2000; Zeldin et al., 2008). We therefore conclude that perceived family support had greater predictive power than perceived social barriers in all of the model's core variables. Kenny & Bledsoe (2005) showed that although the perception of barriers was a negative predictor of attitudes towards education and work, it was a weaker, less robust predictor. The contribution of barriers to our study is relatively insubstantial in comparison to the contribution of support.

Lent et al. (2003) also found a positive influence of social barriers on 'occupational interests'. These authors explained this reversal in the path as the suppression effect of social supports on the barrier/self-efficacy relationship. Under conditions of strongly effective coping, perceived family barriers would not affect interests nor convert goals into actions, because the individuals would seem to see themselves as capable of overcoming such hurdles. It is important to emphasize that those possibilities imply that coping efficacy could have a healthy, beneficial effect on barriers and the coping processes (Lent et al., 2000).

Our findings verified that self-efficacy beliefs did predict interest in science and technology but not outcome expectations or goals, other contextual and personal variables need to be examined more thoroughly to test the claims of the model. In this respect, while the literature reveals an indirect link between parental support and outcome and self-efficacy expectations via performance achievement, the indirect relationships between these variables through other sources of self-efficacy (i.e. vicarious learning, verbal persuasion, physiological activation) have yet to be researched (Garriot et al., 2014). Moreover, it has been confirmed that barriers and supports correlate with each other, so that the greater the perception of social support, the lower the perceived barriers, and vice-versa (Lent et al., 2001; Lent et al., 2003; Sheu et al., 2010). Nonetheless, this result was only apparent in girls. Perceived family barriers and the relationship with the other variables being examined represented the only gender difference found in the study. Whereas in girls there was a significant negative

correlation with perceived family supports and also with outcome expectations and goals, boys only displayed a single, positive link with interest. These differences may be explained by the coping perspectives mentioned above. From childhood, women normally perceive a greater number of barriers in their academic and professional development (Lent et al., 2000). This may lead to greater resilience, added to the current results that supports have greater weight. Conversely, boys are less accustomed to such a perception of barriers, with the result that, despite the lack of significant correlation between perceived family barriers and self-efficacy beliefs, in the model those barriers feature as an element predicting their own beliefs, so that they affect boys more than girls (Flores et al., 2006). In girls we found that there was not even a correlation with self-efficacy beliefs. These findings suggest that other personal variables, not examined in our study, may account for the variance in high school students' technology self-efficacy. The influence of perceived family supports and barriers on efficacy has been demonstrated in short- and medium-term goals in technology courses in boys at secondary school, while in girls, interests and outcome expectations had a greater influence. Finally, we also reported results for another personal factor which has not yet been examined by studies validating the SCCT model. Our study showed that emotional state influenced all of the model's core variables regardless of gender. In fact, the influence of this psychological factor was higher than when all social supports and barriers (family, teacher, peer and financial) were taken into account (Rodríguez-Menéndez et al., 2016). The effect of emotional state on interest, seen more strongly in girls than boys, could be a reason why women do not follow careers in technology fields, despite getting similar marks in these subjects. In addition, the correlation between emotional state and perceived family supports and barriers could be understood as the need to have these two factors in the model.

This study aims to contribute to the literature on an understudied topic, the role of the family in career decisions within the SCCT model. Our research represents progress in

comparison to previous studies since it analyzes the role of perceived family supports and barriers in the SCCT model in greater depth. These results should encourage researchers and counselors to think critically about how contextual factors, particularly perceived family supports/barriers, influence self-efficacy beliefs, outcome expectations, interests and goals. The influence of perceived family supports plays a predominant role in students' career development processes, given that it provides an important basis for planning future studies in a careful and reflexive manner while at school (Boerchi & Tagliabue, 2018). We conclude that our results confirmed the efficacy of the SCCT model in explaining secondary school students' occupational development. Our research clearly confirmed the influence of secondary school students' perceptions about obstacles and encouragement found in their family environments regarding beliefs about their own capacity for achievement, their perception of positive consequences of studying science-technology subjects, and their interest in such courses.

The study indicated that this model could provide a good theoretical starting point for developing career guidance programs. Hence, it is necessary to influence the design of career development programs which may allow educators, counselors and families to address the issue of high school students not wanting to pursue science-technology careers. Students can explore their parents' messages about their options and decision-making about university courses, as well as considering the messages perceived as supports or barriers, and which of these they choose to accept, along with their consequences (Fouad et al., 2016).

The vast majority of research promotes specific interventions for women to improve their self-efficacy beliefs and interest in the technology field. Nevertheless, given the results of the study, we suggest that interventions with boys should not be neglected in secondary schools, since perceived family barriers influence their self-efficacy beliefs in technology subjects and their career interests, even though they do not affect expectations, results or goals.

Accordingly, we highlight the need to implement programs in secondary schools to improve the development of students' self-efficacy beliefs. To sum up, the education system and other social institutions still perceive mathematics, technology/computing and science as 'male domains'. Consequently, it seems that parents, teachers, counsellors and other significant people may promote certain beliefs about academic choices as being more suitable for boys or girls. Thus, counselors should work with both girls and boys to help them recognize their potential and not to self-limit their academic options when they think they are incapable of successfully coping with technology courses.

The assessment of programs for the development of self-efficacy beliefs has demonstrated their effectiveness (Scott & Ciani, 2008). It would also be advantageous to design interventions to help students avoid stress and anxiety in relation to technology courses. It is important to stress that our study included the personal variable 'emotional state'. There is a need for further research to analyse the role of this variable in the SCCT model and test whether the results from our study can be corroborated in cross-national and cross-cultural studies. Since low interest in technology impacts the goals involved in completing an engineering degree (Inda-Caro et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Menéndez et al., 2016), secondary school counsellors, teachers and parents should encourage optimal science-technology career development in adolescents. 'Teachers and school counselors should be more sensitive to an understanding of students' perceptions of their parents' goals or motivating styles and how those perceptions are connected to their own motivational practices' (Kim, 2015, p. 427).

Finally, in comparison with efforts to improve STEM instruction in schools, researchers and practitioners have paid relatively little attention to developing connections between schools, families, and communities (Sheldon & Epstein, 2005). Our study shows the importance of parents in their children's academic choices and career decisions. Any program or intervention to improve interest in technology or academic performance needs to involve

the family. Teachers, educators and counsellors should encourage and guide parents to participate in and support their children's STEM education and learning. In short, we believe that developing partnerships between schools, families and the community could help to improve programs and school environments (Epstein, 2010).

Limitations and Directions for Future Research

The study also has some limitations. The first has to do with the sample, which was from secondary students in a specific region of Spain (Asturias). It consisted of mainly Caucasian students, which means we should be cautious when generalizing results to international contexts, cultures and age groups. It would therefore be beneficial to repeat the study with a more diverse sample. Moreover, it should be remembered that the cross-sectional nature of our study prevents us from making causal inferences. Thus, future research would need to use longitudinal or experimental methods.

These results suggest a variety of lines for future research and offer some important points for career counselors and families working with secondary school students. Future research should analyze the influence of other types of social support/barriers (friends, teachers) on career development. We concluded that family barriers and supports had a direct effect on self-efficacy beliefs. These assumptions did not form part of the original model (Lent et al., 1994), consequently it is theoretically possible that other variables may also be fundamental in the development of the SCCT model. Future research should also explore the positive relationship between perceived parental barriers and interest in diverse gender groups, or focus on specific gender studies, explaining the influence of perceived family barriers on self-efficacy beliefs in boys in greater detail. Therefore, qualitative methods may be helpful in efforts to gain a more in-depth understanding of the influence of contextual background variables on self-efficacy beliefs, outcome expectations, interests and goals, aiming to improve the Spanish workforce's ability to meet the needs of a technological society.

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